

Heterocyclic System II¹. Electrophilic Substitution on 1-Phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole

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A comparative study as to the ease of substitution in phenol, pyrazole and benzene has been done by subjecting 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (I) to halogenation and nitration. Halogenation (mono- or di-) takes place at the phenol moiety. Chlorination and bromination in acetic acid medium furnish 1-phenyl-4-(3,5-dihalogeno-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole(III) and (VI) respectively. Bromination and iodination in refluxing benzene medium produce the respective 1-phenyl-4-(5-halogeno-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IV) and (V). The pyrazole (I) produces 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IX) on nitration with mixed acid.

PYRAZOLE nucleus is highly stabilised and possesses many properties of aromatic compounds. It has been compared to some extent with benzene with regards to ease of substitution. That pyrazole is more easily substituted than benzene is seen in the bromination of 3-phenyl-5-chloropyrazole to 3-phenyl-4-bromo-5-chloropyrazole². Even 1-phenylpyrazoles that contain a benzene nucleus seemingly as activated as N-acylated aniline also undergo halogenation at position-4 of the pyrazole ring. Though substitution at 4 position of pyrazole is very common, that at the other position when position 4 is blocked is not rare. Bromination of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-bromopyrazole gave a 4,5-dibromocompound⁴. This report goes against the finding of Finar *et al*⁵ who obtained 1-(*o*-bromophenyl)-3-methyl-4-bromopyrazole, not the 4, 5-dibromocompound, by bromination of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazole. There are many other contradictory reports and/or uncertainties about the position of substitution in 1-phenylpyrazole system,^{6,7} and there is not a single datum in literature to show how 1-phenylpyrazole system, the pyrazole ring of which is deactivated by the presence of an electron withdrawing group, will behave towards substitution by halogens. Again, though it is generally believed that pyrazole is less susceptible than phenol towards electrophilic substitution⁸, no detailed study about the ease of their substitution has been done. So we wanted to throw some new lights on the points raised above and to make simultaneously a comparative study about the relative ease of substitution in an activated benzene, a pyrazole deactivated by the presence of an electron withdrawing group at position 4 and a deactivated phenol, all the moieties remaining incorporated in the same substrate. Such a substrate is offered by 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole(I).

	X	Y	Z
I	H	H	H
II	Cl	H	H
III	Cl	Cl	H
IV	Br	H	H
V	I	H	H
VI	Br	Br	H
VII	Cl	Br	H
VIII	NO ₂	H	H
IX	H	H	NO ₂

The pyrazole (I) was subjected to chlorination, bromination and iodination, and the mass spectral analysis of the halogenated products was done. In addition to the molecular ion (base peak), four other principal fragments A], [B], [C] and [D] were obtained¹. These fragments clearly indicated that substitution (mono- or di-) had taken place at the phenol moiety of the pyrazole (I).

Chlorination of the pyrazole (I) in warm acetic acid gave a dichlorocompound. That one of the two chlorine atoms in this dichlorocompound was located in *p*-position of the hydroxygroup, was proved by chlorinating 1-phenyl-4-(5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzoyl) pyrazole(II) when the same dichlorocompound resulted in. On general ground (mesomeric effects of electron donating hydroxygroup and electron withdrawing carbonyl function), the structure

of 1-phenyl-4-(3,5-dichloro-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole(III) was assigned to this dichlorocompound. Its nmr spectrum τ —2.03(1H, br, ArOH), 1.53(1H, s, pyrazole H_a), 1.83(1H, s, pyrazole H_b), 2.27(1H, d, J 2Hz, ArH *ortho* to chloro- and carbonyl functions), 2.42(1H, d, J 2Hz, ArH *ortho* to two chloro-groups) and 2.81(5H, s, ArH), is also compatible with this structure (III). Bromination and iodination of the pyrazole(I) in refluxing benzene solution gave monohalogenated products, whereas bromination in acetic acid medium produced a dibromocompound. The structures (IV), (V) and (VI) were assigned to the monobromo-, monoiodo- and dibromo- products respectively. The structures (IV) and (VI) were also confirmed by independent syntheses. The structure of the iodo-product was deduced as (V) from analogy with the monobromocompound(IV). The chlorocompound(II) and the monobromocompound(IV) could be further brominated to the dihalogenated products(VII) and (VI) respectively. The pyrazole(I) could not be iodinated in acetic acid medium.

A cursory look at the structure of the substrate (I) would reveal that the carbonyl group deactivates both phenol and pyrazole almost to the same extent. So the substitution reaction of the compound(I) is tantamount to the comparison of the relative ease of substitution in at least 2-substituted phenol and 4-substituted pyrazole, if not proper phenol and pyrazole themselves, under absolutely identical conditions. The substrate(I) offers another advantage as to examine whether the activity of a slightly deactivated pyrazole is equal to, or more or less than that of N-acylated aniline. Halogenation, particularly dichlorination and dibromination data, clearly show that phenol is much more reactive than pyrazole as well as the benzene nucleus of 1-phenylpyrazole.

Nitration of the pyrazole (I) with mixed acid gave a mononitro derivative. Had the nitration the same trend as that of halogenation, one would expect the formation of 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzoyl)pyrazole (VIII). An authentic sample of the pyrazole (VIII) was prepared, but it was found to be different from the nitration product of the

pyrazole (I). Oxidative degradation of this nitroproduct to 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)pyrazole-4-carboxylic acid⁹ suggested it to have the structure of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IX), and the prepared authentic sample of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)pyrazole (IX) was found to be identical with it. The nitrosubstitution at the benzene nucleus of 1-phenylpyrazole (I) in preference to either at hydroxyphenyl or at pyrazole ring can be rationalised as follows. In concentrated sulphuric acid medium as used for nitration purpose, the phenol moiety undergoes at first sulphonation at *para* position to the hydroxy group (as in preparation of *o*-bromophenol from phenol¹⁰) and thus becomes deactivated, the sulphonic acid group being knocked off at a later stage during work up. Pyrazole ring of 1-phenylpyrazole is also deactivated¹¹ in acid medium by getting protonated at position², but the 1-phenyl moiety is little affected. It is also recorded in literature¹² that 1-phenylpyrazoles having electron withdrawing substituent as carboxylic attached to the pyrazole ring nitrate only in the *para*-position of the benzene ring. It may be further mentioned here that salicylic acid on nitration with 15% nitric acid yields 5-nitrosalicylic acid¹³ whereas nitration of a solution of salicylic acid in conc. sulfuric acid with mixed acid gave exclusively 3-nitrosalicylic acid¹⁴ in our hand. This experiment clearly indicates that though salicylic acid is not completely deactivated in sulfuric acid medium, at least its position 5 is blocked by sulfonation. In nitration of the pyrazole (I) we obtained the nitroproduct (IX) in 50% yield; it might be the case that some 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-nitrobenzoyl)pyrazole was also formed, which we failed to isolate.

1-Phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (I) and the authentic samples of the substituted pyrazoles(II, IV, VI and VIII) could be prepared by refluxing the phenylhydrazones (X) of properly substituted 4-oxo-4*H*-[1]benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes in ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution¹. Later on, it was found that generation of the aldehyde function by cleavage of the pyrone ring at C-2 with hydroxide anion¹⁵ was not necessary for the formation of the pyrazole ring. The phenylhydrazones (X) on refluxing in glacial acetic acid gave rise to the desired pyrazoles. In this case, the intramolecular nucleophilic attack takes place at C₂ with concomitant opening of the pyrone ring as shown in Scheme 1.

The cyclisation reaction as depicted in Scheme 1 demands that the hydrazones (X) must exist in Z-isomeric form. Nothing can be said definitely about

Scheme - 1

the stereochemistry of the hydrazones. Had they existed in E-form, they must have isomerised to Z-form under reaction conditions.

The preparation of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl) pyrazole (IX) deserves special mention. *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazone (XI) of 4-oxo-4*H*-[1]-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehyde failed to produce the compound (IX) when refluxed in ethanolic potassium hydroxide solution. Here the intermediate aldehyde (XII)¹⁵ perhaps underwent deformation before the aldehyde function could combine with the phenylhydrazino group of weak nucleophilicity. The hydrozone (XI) evaded the conversion as depicted in Scheme I when refluxed in acetic acid, whereas the same conversion to the pyrazole (IX) was made possible by refluxing it in ethylene glycol. So it is certain that thermal energy rather than solubility of the hydrazones (X) and (XI) influences the cyclisation reaction.

Experimental

N.m.r spectra were measured with a Varian T60 60MHz spectrometer in CDCl_3 solution with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were determined with a Hitachi RMU-6L spectrometer at 80eV using the direct inlet system. Melting points were taken in open capillaries in a sulfuric acid bath. Pet. ether refers to the fraction of b.p. 40-60°.

Preparation of the pyrazoles (I, II, IV and VIII) : The phenylhydrazone (X, X=Y=H)¹ (0.50 g) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 1 hr., cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol in light yellow crystals (0.44 g) of 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole(I), mp. 113°, (lit.¹ m.p. 113°)

Similar treatment of the phenylhydrazones (X)¹ of the properly substituted 3-formylchromones gave in approximately 80% yields the pyrazole(II), m.p. 146° (EtOH) (lit.¹, m.p. 145°), the bromopyrazole (IV), m.p. 154° (CHCl_3), and the nitro pyrazole (VIII), m.p. 207° (EtOH).

Chlorination of the pyrazole (I) : Chlorine was passed into a warm solution of the pyrazole (I) (0.50 g) in acetic acid (10 ml) for 1 min. The solution was cooled in ice when 1-phenyl-4-(3,5-dichloro-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (III) separated as a solid

(0.49 g). Crystallisation from chloroform gave lightly yellow crystals, m.p. 182-4°; acetate, m.p. 121-2° (CHCl_3).

The pyrazole (II) (0.60 g) was similarly chlorinated to the dichloro compound (III) (0.60 g).

Bromination of the pyrazole(I) in benzene medium : The pyrazole (I) (0.10 g) was refluxed with bromine (0.5 ml) in benzene (20 ml) for 3 hr. The mixture was then cooled, washed with sodium bisulfite solution and water. Benzene layer was dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to afford 1-phenyl-4-(5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IV) (0.09 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 154° (CHCl_3); acetate, m.p. and m.m.p. 132° (CHCl_3 -Pet. ether).

Iodination of the pyrazole (I) : The pyrazole (I) (0.40 g) was refluxed with iodine (1.0 g) in benzene (40 ml) for 4 hr. Similar processing of the reaction mixture as in case of bromination yielded yellow crystals of 1-phenyl-4-(5-iodo-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (V) (0.39 g), m.p. 143° (EtOAc), ν_{max} (nujol) 1670 (w, CO); *m/e* 390 (M^+), 246, 218, 171 and 144. Its acetate was a low melting solid.

Bromination of the pyrazole (I) in acetic acid medium : The pyrazole (I) (0.40 g) was refluxed with bromine (3 ml) in acetic acid (10 ml) for 3 hr., then poured into water (40 ml). 1-Phenyl-4-(3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole(VI) (0.44 g) was collected by filtration. Recrystallisation from chloroform afforded needle shaped yellow crystals, m.p. and m.m.p. 179°; τ -2.41(1H, br, ArOH), 1.58 (1H, s, pyrazole H_8), 1.90 (1H, s, pyrazole H_5), 2.08 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, ArH *ortho* to bromo and carbonyl groups), 2.37 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, ArH *ortho* to two bromo groups) and 2.77 (5H, s, ArH); *m/e* 422, 420, 418, 280, 278, 276, 171 and 144; acetate, m.p. and m.m.p. 165-8° (CHCl_3).

The bromopyrazole(III) (0.12 g) and the chloropyrazole (II) (0.10 g) on similar treatment with bromine afforded respectively the dibromocompound (VI) (0.11 g) and the chlorobromocompound (VI1) (0.09 g), m.p. 171° (CHCl_3); acetate, m.p. 147° (CHCl_3).

Nitration of the pyrazole (I) : The pyrazole (I) (0.20 g) was added in small lots to a well cooled mixture of conc. sulfuric acid (5 ml) and conc. nitric acid (5 ml). After the addition was over, the mixture was warmed on a water bath for 30 min., cooled and then poured over ice. The separated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to afford yellow crystals of 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IX) (0.12 g), m.p. and m.m.p. 191-3°; acetate, m.p. and m.m.p. 150° (CHCl_3).

Oxidation of the nitro compound (IX) : The above nitrophenylpyrazole (IX) (0.50 g) was oxidised with chromic acid according to the procedure¹ described for the oxidation of the parent pyrazole(I) to furnish

1-p-nitrophenylpyrazole-4-carboxylic acid (0.12 g), m.p. 247° (CHCl₃) (lit.⁹, m. p. 250°). Its mass spectrum showed peaks at *m/e* 233 (M⁺), 216 (M-OH), 203 (M-NO) and 187 (M-NO-OH).

Authentic sample of 1-phenyl-4-(3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (VI) ;

2,4-Dibromophenol was prepared according to the method of Pope *et. al.*¹⁶. On adding bromine (120 g, 39 ml) dissolved in hydrobromic acid (40 ml) to a suspension of phenol (35.5 g) in hydrobromic acid (10 ml) at below 0° was obtained 2,4-dibromophenol (47 g), m.p. 40° (lit.¹⁶, m.p. 40°) which on being refluxed with acetic anhydride (30 ml) and a few drops of conc. sulphuric acid afforded 2,4-dibromophenyl acetate (49.0 g) b. p. 160-5°/15 mm. The above acetate (30 g) was subjected to Fries rearrangement¹⁷ and after usual work up 3,5-dibromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone (14.0 g), m.p. 106° (lit.¹⁷, m.p. 110°) was obtained.

A solution of the above acetophenone (14.0 g) in DMF (10.0 ml) was added to the formylating complex prepared from phosphorus oxychloride (8.20 ml) and DMF (20.0 ml)¹⁸. After usual workup, 6,8-dibromochromone-3-aldehyde (6.0 g), m.p. 174° (lit.¹⁸, m.p. 177-8°) was obtained.

A mixture of the above chromone-aldehyde (3.30 g, 0.01 mole) and phenylhydrazine (1.08 g, 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20.0 ml) was warmed when the hydrazone (X, X=Y=Br) (4.20 g) separated out, which without further purification was refluxed in acetic acid (15.0 ml) for 2 hr to afford the pyrazole (VI) (3.98 g), m.p. 179° (CHCl₃); acetate, m.p. 168° (CHCl₃).

Authentic sample of 1-(p-nitrophenyl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IX) : A mixture of 3-formylchromone (1.74 g, 0.01 mole) and *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine (1.53 g, 0.01 mole) was refluxed in ethanol for 1 hr. On removal of ethanol was obtained the hydrazone (XI) (3.0 g), m. p. 248-50° (acetic acid), which was refluxed with ethylene glycol (15.0 ml) for 6 hr., cooled and diluted with water. The precipitated solid was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to afford the nitrophenylpyrazole (IX) (2.6 g), m. p. 191°; acetate, m. p. 150° (CHCl₃)

3-Nitrosalicylic acid : To a cooled solution of salicylic acid (1.0 g) in conc. sulfuric acid (20 ml) was added conc. nitric acid (10 ml) slowly. After the addition was over, the mixture was warmed for 14 min, then poured over ice when 3-nitrosalicylic acid (0.98 g), m.p. 126° (water) (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 125°), amide, m.p. 142° (lit.¹⁴, m.p. 145°) was obtained.

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